

MAA in proposal evaluation

TOOLSHEET

Purpose

This discussion paper analyzes how the multi-actor approach (MAA) has been evaluated in Horizon 2020 and Horizon Europe proposals. It shows you how the understanding of the MAA by the official proposal evaluators has evolved and what they look for in an MAA project proposal. You learn about key concepts such as 'Evaluation Summary Reports' and 'Rubric'.

Benefits

A large and essential part of developing a successful MA project proposal consists of concisely, clearly and specifically describing how your MA project consortium will apply the MAA. Understanding what proposal evaluators look for in this description, can help you in finding the right language and structure for your MA project proposal thus increasing your chance of success.

Practical recommendations

We provide an abstract of the report here. The most pertinent information to read in the report itself is Chapter 5 (p. 8-13) collating useful evaluation statements on the MAA and to study the 'rubric' for MAA proposal preparation and evaluation (p. 17-24).

- **Analysis of how the Multi-Actor Approach (MAA) is evaluated in Horizon Proposals:**
 - 67 Evaluation Summary Reports (ESRs) of project proposals for calls under Horizon 2020 and Horizon Europe applying the MAA are analysed;
 - An ESR is the jointly developed report by the evaluation team for a distinct call for proposals. The ESR of every Horizon proposal has to explain to what extent applicants address the requested objectives, scope and additional requirements such as the incorporation of the MAA;
 - Analysis provides insights into how evaluators assess the quality and effectiveness of the MAA in the proposals.

Applicability box

Main MA Skills supported

Transparent communication about agenda's, expectations and results

Be comfortable with co-ownership and responsibility of tasks, results, and outcomes

Relevant Target groups

All

Useful link(s)

[Discussion paper no. 1 on MAA project proposal evaluation](#)

- **Trends and evolution of the understanding and evaluation of the MAA:**
 - The analysis provides examples of statements from the ESR on what evaluators found positive and negative about MAA in project proposals;
 - Most evaluation statements relate to the appropriateness of the applied methodology, the correct use of terminology, whether or not key stakeholder groups are accurately identified, and whether the proposal sufficiently considers how each stakeholder group will be included during project implementation.

- **Recommendations: Rubric for Multi-Actor Proposal Development and Evaluation:**
 - A 'rubric' is a learning and assessment tool which helps in setting clear criteria and levels of quality for these criteria. A more elaborate explanation is given in the report;
 - The rubric on MAA describes nine different components or criteria of the MAA definition used in Cluster 6 of Horizon Europe and sets five quality levels (insufficient, routine, good, great, exemplary);
 - It offers practical recommendations for researchers to enhance their multi-actor strategies. These include early stakeholder engagement, clear communication plans, and continuous feedback mechanisms.

Rubric as a Reflective Tool

This rubric has been developed using different sources such as the 67 Evaluation Summary Reports of Horizon 2020 and Horizon Europe MAA project proposals, the work done by the H2020 project LIAISON and rubrics in related fields (such as the one on Responsible Research and Innovation by Wickson and Carew (2014), and one on networking agroecology demonstration farms by McGreevy et al. (2021)).

We believe using this Rubric as a reference while designing, writing and revising, you can keep track of your consortium's progress and jointly evaluate what quality level your MA project proposals reaches for each of the nine components.